

CASPR-2 Mediated Encephalitis with Single Discrete Delusion: A case Report

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ABSTRACT

Contactin Associated Protein-Like Receptor 2 (CASPR-2) -mediated encephalitis is characterized by multiple psychiatric symptoms; however, its presentation with a single discrete delusion is unusual. Here, we report a 63-year-old man who presented with a single delusion at an outpatient clinic and was diagnosed with CASPR-2-mediated encephalitis after multiple follow-up visits and investigations. The patient showed improvement after treatment with the dissolution of the delusion. This is the first reported case of CASPR-2-mediated encephalitis with a single discrete delusion, and further studies are needed to explore the relationship between CASPR-2 and this unusual presentation.

Keywords: CASPR-2 encephalitis; Single discrete delusion; Case report; Outcome; Unique presentation

INTRODUCTION

CASPR-2-mediated encephalitis is an autoimmune neurological condition caused by the formation of autoantibodies against the CASPR-2 protein. Structurally, this protein is a cellular transmembrane adhesion molecule with its C-terminal part interacting with an ankyrin protein that connects juxta paranodal and paranodal complexes with the axonal cytoskeleton. Antibodies formed against these specific parts of a neuron can have varied effects. Although these proteins are located throughout the neuraxis, their populations in the central nervous system (CNS) are specifically dense in the limbic system and basal ganglia compared to other cortices. Therefore, the symptoms that arise in pathologies involving these areas manifest as confusion, disorientation, hallucinations, and difficulty forming new memories. Immunological response against CASPR-2 protein is also associated with other neurological conditions such as Guillain-Barre syndrome, neurodevelopmental cognitive disorders including autism spectrum disorder, dyslexia and language impairment, epilepsy, and schizophrenia. There are also several well-known PNS effects of this entity, including neuropathic pain, dysautonomia, and muscle cramps, to name a few. Here, we present a 63-old man reported with a chief complaint of isolated delusion. After undergoing extensive investigations, he was diagnosed with CASPR-2-

mediated encephalitis. A combination of immunosuppressive and cognitive behavioral therapy was utilized for treatment, and his symptoms resolved thoroughly. This case highlights the possibility that CASPR-2-mediated encephalitis can present with a single discrete psychotic symptom.

CASE PRESENTATION

AG is a 63-year-old man with a history of Hepatitis B and compensated liver disease who presented with a two-week history of altered mental status. This 'altered mental status' was characterized by a discrete delusion. As described by the patient's son, the patient started believing he was the owner of a "4000-acre land," which was contrary to the truth. He also developed new-onset mistrust in his children, which the family had never observed before. He was also noted to quarrel with his wife, which, according to the patient's son, had never happened in the past. There were no hallucinations. There was no history of unilateral vision, weakness, numbness, balance, or language problems. His neurological exam revealed that he was alert and oriented to time, place, person, and situation. He was able to follow commands and was able to hold an in-depth conversation. His cranial nerves were normal, and the rest of the Neurological exam was non-revealing. He was admitted to the hospital with a working diagnosis of acute psychosis due to the underlying liver disease. His Liver enzymes were mildly elevated, which was his baseline over the last six months. This included Aspartate Transaminase (AST) of 58 U/L (0-41 U/L) and Alanine Transaminase (ALT) of 51 U/L (0-41 U/L), Gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) of 70 U/L (<55 U/L) while on Tenofovir. His initial labs showed some element of acute kidney injury, evidenced by raised serum creatinine (Cr) of 1.22 mg/dL along with Blood Urea Nitrogen (BUN) of 28 mg/dL. His serum Sodium was low at 119 mmol/L (135-145 mmol/L). Serum Ammonia was normal. Serum Glucose was also normal. Serum Ceruloplasmin was not low. His Urinalysis (UA) and Chest X-ray (CXR) showed no signs of infection. His complete blood count (CBC) did not show any abnormality. Pan Computed tomography (CT) did not show any evidence of malignancy. The patient was treated symptomatically with IV normal saline and antipsychotics such as Quetiapine. He showed improvement in serum Creatinine, BUN, and Sodium, along with some improvement in Liver enzymes. However, his specific delusional thought process persisted. Neurology was consulted at this moment, and MRI Brain with contrast showed mild diffuse atrophy and no diffusion restriction to suggest an acute stroke. There was no abnormal enhancement. In summary, no lesion on the brain MRI could explain the patient's symptoms. Because of the ongoing Coronavirus Pandemic, Coronavirus PCR and Anti-SARS CoV antibodies were also sent, which were negative. An ElectroEncephaloGram (EEG) was obtained, which showed no focal signs of cortical irritability. The EEG only showed signs of mild encephalopathy, evidenced by mild diffuse slowing. At this point in time, we were considering encephalitis as a possible cause of the patient's presentation, and the next step was to go for cerebrospinal fluids (CSF) sampling. However, the patient refused the Lumbar puncture. A serum for autoimmune encephalitis panel was sent, which came back positive for Contain-associated Protein 2 (CASPR-2) antibodies. At this point in time, the diagnosis of CASPR-2-mediated encephalitis was made. The patient was started on IV steroids for three days with a slow taper over a month. Initial high-dose steroids did not do much; however, the patient's delusional thought process resolved entirely in roughly one and a half months. The patient's liver disease remained stable. Follow-up repeats autoimmune encephalitis panel was negative for CASPR-2 antibodies a couple of months later. The patient was lost to further follow-up. To our knowledge and research, this will be the first reported case of a patient with CASPR-2-mediated encephalitis presenting as a single discrete delusion.

DISCUSSION

Contactin Associated Protein-Like Receptor (CASPR) is a group of cell adhesion molecules (CAM) found both in the CNS as well as peripheral nervous system (PNS). These adhesion molecules have sub-populations with distribution varying throughout the CNS and PNS.^[1] Their distribution varies in the neuron itself and the neuronal circuitry.^[2] For example, A type of CASPR 2 sub-population may be more abundant in the brain's limbic system than the peripheral nervous system. Even within a neuron, their location varies around the node of Ranvier and the adjacent areas called the paranodes.^[2] For this reason, an antibody directed against a specific region may have varied phenotypic presentations.^[3] These presentations can frequently have behavioral manifestations such as delusions, hallucinations, personality changes, cognitive problems, sleep-wake cycle disturbances, and well-known PNS manifestations.

We present a case of acute onset isolated delusion in a 63-year-old gentleman. He did not have any personal history of psychiatric disease nor a family history of it. He did have compensated liver disease due to hepatitis B. His liver disease was stable, and he did not have any evidence of liver cancer. Since the patient was lost to follow-up, we could not find a reason for the diagnosis of CASPR-2 encephalitis. However, with the limited follow-up that the patient had with us, he improved completely with the resolution of his symptom and repeat testing showing negative CASPR-2 Ab titer. Although patients with CASPR-2 encephalitis are known to have psychiatric symptoms, to our knowledge and research, an isolated psychiatric symptom has not been reported in the literature so far.^[4-6] We want to point out the significance of this knowledge to our psychiatry and medicine colleagues, as this presentation can frequently be misread and mislabelled as acute psychosis or schizophreniform disorder or etcetera^[7,8]. More importantly, these diagnoses are frequently managed symptomatically without going beyond basic investigations to find an underlying cause. It can worsen and progress if untreated, although some studies have noted a spontaneous resolution.^[9] There is no current guideline for treating this disorder; however, similar principles used in other autoimmune conditions apply to improvement in patient symptoms.^[10] Our patient was treated symptomatically with antipsychotics as well as oral prednisone. It took roughly six weeks for the patient to return to his prior baseline following oral prednisone, which was gradually tapered once the symptoms resolved. Cognitive behavioral therapy was also utilized for delusional thoughts. General physicians, psychiatrists, and neurologists should be vigilant in taking the history of such a patient. In this case, the family was instrumental in noticing a sudden change and bringing the patient to the Neurology clinic. Acute onset of psychiatric symptoms in a patient with a previous no history of the psychiatric disease should prompt the physician to try to find out the underlying secondary cause.

CONCLUSION

CASPR-2-mediated encephalitis usually presents with a myriad of symptoms related to CNS and PNS. However, it can present with an isolated psychotic symptom such as delusion. Therefore, a patient presenting with new-onset psychotic symptoms should be thoroughly investigated for an underlying new pathology, especially encephalitis, driving the presentation. Timely recognition and treatment can lead to a better outcome.

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